

Synthesis and characterization of polyurethanes using the reaction of hexamethylene diisocyanate with varying combinations of telechelic carbonaceous and PDMS glycols

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Polyurethane resins were synthesised by reacting 1,6-hexamethylene diisocyanate with mixture of macroglycols such as telechelic dihydroxyl diphenyl dimethyl siloxane (ϕ_2 PDMS) and polytetramethylene glycol (PTG) in different proportions and chain extender butane diol (BD) in presence of dibutyl tin dilaurate (DIBTDL) catalyst to obtain three types of elastomers such as neat polyurethane (PU), copolyurethane-siloxane (PUPS) and neat polysiloxane-urethane (PS) elastomers in which PU or PS elastomer was derived from the reaction of diisocyanate with a single macroglycol PTG or ϕ_2 PDMS respectively whereas PUPS elastomer corresponds to mixtures of macroglycols (PTG + ϕ_2 PDMS) along with BD chain extender. Solvent absorption properties of elastomers were studied and it was observed that the hydrophobic character of these elastomers increases with the incorporation of HO ϕ_2 PDMS macroglycol component in the elastomer system. Thermogravimetric analysis reveals that in the given condition (heating rate 10°C/min) all of these elastomers are thermally quite stable upto 200°C; and the Char yield at 500°C increases with the incorporation of ϕ_2 PDMS component in the elastomer.

Keywords: Polyurethane, PDMS, copolymer, elastomer, glycol.

Introduction

Advances in synthetic polymer chemistry have transformed the design of 1D, 2D or 3D network of synthetic polymers for value-added commercial applications^{1,2}. Organization of discrete sequences of chemically distinct repeat units into multiblock architectures provides researchers with nearly unlimited scopes for creating products². Segmented polyurethanes (PU) prepared by condensation polymerization of diisocyanate and dihydroxy compounds (monomers and oligomers or polymers), represent an important class of such multiblock polymers^{3,4}. Polyurethane elastomers (PUE) are a special class of polymer to offer several advantages like lightness, adhesion and abrasion resistant characteristics^{4,5}. But PU also suffers from disadvantages that it has limited heat stability compared to silicone based resin system. Researchers are all out in search for polymeric materials to overcome the deficiencies of polyurethane resin (PU)⁴⁻⁷.

Polydimethylsiloxane is commonly known by the acronym PDMS belongs to a group of polymeric organosilicon

compounds and is specially known for its inertness, non-flammability, and special rheological properties^{8,9}. It is expected that copolymer with molecular composition comprising silicone moiety as well as urethane moiety may exhibit improved thermal stability at the same time can afford to provide useful mechanical and thermal properties. Such copolymers are expected to exhibit useful properties at wide range of temperature particularly for uses at different geographical environments of diverse climatic conditions. With this background of information, work has been undertaken to synthesise a series of polyurethane copolymers containing a combination of hexamethylene diisocyanate (HDI) and mixture of macroglycols comprising carbonaceous macroglycol (PTG) and organo-inorganic macroglycol (ϕ_2 PDMS) such that the organic moiety through urethane linkages as well as inorganic moiety through siloxane linkages can be created in the elastomer matrix network².

Telechelic dihydroxyl diphenyl dimethyl siloxane (ϕ_2 PDMS) belongs to PDMS family; and to the best of our knowledge, there is no information available in the literature

about the modification of polyurethane resin with this particular kind of PDMS such as ϕ_2 PDMS^{7,8}.

Experimental

Silicon containing macroglycol such as telechelic dihydroxyl poly(dimethylsiloxane-co-diphenylsiloxane) (Fig. 1, ϕ_2 PDMS, a modified form of PDMS) was procured from Sigma-Aldrich in which 5 molar% of SiPh₂O was present.

Fig. 1. α,ω -Dihydroxyl poly(dimethylsiloxane-co-diphenylsiloxane), $\text{HOSi}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2\text{O}[\text{Si}(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{O}]_m[\text{Si}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2\text{O}]_n\text{Si}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_5)_2\text{OH}$) (acronymed as ϕ_2 PDMS), a modified form of PDMS.

The carbonaceous macroglycol such as polyteramethylene glycol (PTG) of mol. wt. 2000 was procured from Sigma-Aldrich. Solvent tetrahydrofuran (THF), and catalyst dibutyl tin dilaurate (DBTDL) were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich. 1,4-Butane diol (BD), 1,6-hexamethylene diisocyanate (HDI) and n-hexane were procured from Acros.

Spectroscopy: ATR-FTIR (Nicolet) with a resolution of 1 cm^{-1} was scanned from 400–4000 cm^{-1} at room temperature to study the functional groups of polyurethane and other samples.

Thermal analysis: A TGA (thermogravimetric analysis) thermal instrument (DuPont, 951 TGA) was used to scan at a rate of 10°C min^{-1} for analysis. Oxygen-free nitrogen stream of 40 mL min^{-1} was maintained through the cell during measurement.

Results and discussion

Preparation of resin: Copolymers were prepared in accordance with the following reactions are scheme:

where, $x = 1$ for PU, $x < 1$ for PUPS, $x = 0$ for PS

First PTG was taken in the solvent tetrahydrofuran (THF) followed by addition of PDMS and HDI step by step in presence of 0.75×10^{-4} M, DBTDL. The mixture was heated at 120°C for 3 h followed by addition of butane diol and stirred for another 1 h. THF was removed by applying vacuum and then the overall viscous mixture was cast over a Teflon sheet to obtain the elastomeric sheet of PU, PUPS and PS. Here if there is no use of ϕ_2 PDMS but only PTG as microglycol in the reaction mixture during synthesis of the elastomer, then it is called *neat polyurethane* and is acronymed as PU whereas if it corresponds to 100% ϕ_2 PDMS without any PTG in the mixture, it is called *neat polysiloxane-urethane* elastomer (PS). If the macroglycol composition contains both PTG macroglycol as well as ϕ_2 PDMS in the mixture, then the elastomeric product is called hybrid or copolyurethane-polysiloxane (PUPS) elastomer.

When PTG was taken in THF it gave a transparent solution. But on addition of polysiloxane into this transparent solution, it turned into translucent dispersion. And on addition of HDI on this mixture, it regained its transparency. This transparent solution was stirred constantly in the presence of dibutyltin dilaurate catalyst at 120°C, it turned into a viscous solution which on further heating in presence of chain extender 1,4-butane diol, it turns into a solid.

Incorporation of ϕ_2 PDMS was examined by Energy dispersive X-ray (EDX)¹⁰ and the results of the essential elements in some of the representative samples (Figs. 2a, 2b, 2c) support the incorporation of ϕ_2 PDMS components in the elastomer system in commensurate with the composition of ϕ_2 PDMS macroglycol.

Analysis based on FTIR:

Usually NMR is suitable for characterization of small organic molecules but often not convenient for polymers. The presence of isocyanate group of HDI is clearly visible at 2270 cm^{-1} (Fig. S1) which gets reduced gradually with the progress of reaction with hydroxyl group of the glycols with the formation of PU, PUPS or PS elastomer system. Absence of any absorption in the region¹¹ near 2270 cm^{-1} in any of the samples of elastomer (Figs. S2–S7) clearly indicates completion of reaction between HDI and the glycols. The characteristic consecutive six methylene groups (CH_2)₆ of HDI is understood from the typical absorptions in the range 786–697 cm^{-1} (Figs. S2–S7)^{11–13}.

FTIR spectral data of ϕ_2 PDMS are shown in Fig. S1(a)

Fig. 2. EDAX analysis of (a) PU derived without ϕ_2 PDMS, (b) EDAX analysis of PUPS derived from 10 ϕ_2 PDMS and (c) EDAX analysis of PUPS derived from 20 ϕ_2 PDMS.

which indicated the absorption of terminal OH groups of ϕ_2 PDMS. Two terminal phenyl rings of ϕ_2 PDMS offering steric hindrance to the formation of hydrogen bonding for which OH was detected at a wave number of 3680 cm^{-1} (Fig. S1(a)) which is far away from the usual location of absorption of OH group of commonly available hydroxyl group of organic compounds¹⁴.

Fig. S2, indicates usual FTIR absorptions for the characteristics groups^{14–17} like methylene (CH_2), ether ($-\text{O}-$), $\text{C}=\text{O}$, NH in the sample of PU but it does not show any absorption for aromatic group, thus corroborating absence of ϕ_2 PDMS macroglycol component in PU.

Characteristic bands for siloxane segments in PUPSs are clearly observed in the spectra (Figs. S3–S7). The aromatic sp^2 carbon hydrogen stretching corresponding to ϕ_2 PDMS in the elastomers took place typically near but just above^{11–16} 3000 cm^{-1} as manifested in the form of tiny ripples (3072 and 3052 cm^{-1} shown by arrow marking in Figs. 3, S3–S7) while its aliphatic C-H *sym* and *asym* stretchings due to me-

thyl ($-\text{CH}_3$) group and/or methylene ($-\text{CH}_2-$) groups of different domains are visible very close to but below 3000 cm^{-1} (for example, 2938 and 2858 cm^{-1}) (Fig. S5)^{14–16}. It may be noted that even though such absorptions in this region are closely spaced but it appears the pattern changed noticeably on incorporation of ϕ_2 PDMS from 0 to 100 wt% in the macroglycol composition (minor became major peak intensity and vice versa). Importantly, such doublet below 3000 cm^{-1} changes very systematically in the sense that its higher wave number part gradually decreased from 2940 cm^{-1} to 2937 cm^{-1} and then jumped to 2961 cm^{-1} when the elastomer corresponds to 100% ϕ_2 PDMS. And other absorption also followed more or less the same trend in the sense that such absorption for PU at 2856 cm^{-1} but it jumped to 2932 cm^{-1} when it is observed for PS. Interestingly, with the increase in the proportion of ϕ_2 PDMS in the macroglycol, there is gradual blue shift of such aromatic C-H stretching absorption as understood from the magnified view (Fig. 3) of such tiny ripples. Notably, there is no aromatic $=\text{C}-\text{H}$ stretching

Fig. 3. Magnified view of the region for sp^2 = C-H stretching for PUPS elastomeric samples (A) 10%, (B) 20 wt.%, (C) 30 wt.%, (D) 40 wt.% and (E) 100 wt.% in which the maximum blue shift is for (E) 3072–3052 cm^{-1} .

(so no ripples, Fig. S2) visible in the elastomer PU as no ϕ_2 PDMS was used in its synthesis of PU (Fig. S2).

Characteristic bands for siloxane segments in PUPSs are clearly observed in the spectra (Figs. S3–S7), for example, the absorption bands at 1258 ± 1 cm^{-1} , near 1100 cm^{-1} , and in the range 804 – 795 cm^{-1} where the peak at 1258 ± 1 cm^{-1} is the absorption of Si-C stretching in Si-CH₃; and the absorption near 1100 cm^{-1} is due to the -Si-O-Si- linkages of ϕ_2 PDMS (Figs. S3–S7); whereas the band in the range 804 – 795 cm^{-1} resulted from two CH₃ groups attached to Si as H₃C-Si-CH₃ (Figs. S3–S7)^{16,17}. Out-of-plane C-H deformations are strongly coupled vibrations in the environment of phenyl ring of ϕ_2 PDMS^{14–16} was observed in the range 804 – 795 cm^{-1} where interestingly such absorption is distinctly visible in PS but not in PU; and the absorption gradually red shifted from 804 to 795 cm^{-1} with the incorporation of ϕ_2 PDMS component.

With PU the NH absorption was observed as small but distinctly singular band at 3322 cm^{-1} ¹⁴ corresponding to urethane linkage derived from HDI and PTG in absence of ϕ_2 PDMS (Fig. S2). Similarly, when the urethane is derived from HDI and ϕ_2 PDMS in absence PTG, the NH absorption is observed as a singular band at 3330 cm^{-1} (Fig. S7). But with PUPS, there appeared doublet absorption corresponding to two types of NH groups – one NH environment derived from reaction of HDI and PTG at 3319.5 ± 0.5 cm^{-1} and the other from the combination of HDI and ϕ_2 PDMSiOH at

3347 ± 2 cm^{-1} (Figs. S3–S6). NH absorption near 3319.5 ± 0.5 cm^{-1} is due to the formation of $-(OH_2C)_4ONHCO-$ (urethane linkages) whereas 3347 ± 2 cm^{-1} is for $(-\phi_2SiONHCO-)$ (urethane-siloxane linkages). The absorption 3347 ± 2 cm^{-1} is in commensurate with the weaker hydrogen bonding (Figs. S3–S6) through N-H. The steric hindrance of phenyl groups and lower electronegativity of Si compared to that of C (1.8 vis-à-vis 2.5)¹⁴ causing N-H stretching associated with $\phi_2SiONHCO-$ to absorb relatively at a bit higher energy at 3347 ± 2 cm^{-1} compared to that of $-(OH_2C)_4ONHCO-$ at a relatively lower energy at 3319.5 ± 0.5 cm^{-1} .

Absorption at 13691 ± 1 cm^{-1} is due to C-H bending observed in PU and PUPS elastomers but is not visible in PS derived from macroglycol composition with 100 wt.% ϕ_2 PDMS in macroglycol composition (Fig. S7) and there is a gradual blue shift, even though small but definite as samples composition contains more ϕ_2 PDMS moiety (Figs. S2–S6). It is worthy to note that for such C-H bending requires some environment as breathing space to vibrate. Such C-H bending vibrations are possible in this region so long the matrix contains at least some PTG segment but in PS it is not possible due to the steric hindrance of the phenyl groups of ϕ_2 PDMS segment. The absorption at 1369 ± 1 cm^{-1} indicates N-H of $-CONH(CH_2)_6-$ deformation is most prominent in PU (Fig. S2) but is not visible in PS (Fig. S7). The C-H scissoring deformations are visible in the region¹⁴ of 1477 ± 2 cm^{-1} but their appearance became subdued with incorporation of PDMS moiety (Figs. S2–S7).

However, with PS having 100% of ϕ_2 PDMS as macroglycols, the C=O stretching weakened probably due to the proximity of electron withdrawing effect of phenyl groups^{11–14}. Such effect led C=O to acquire some C-O character and influenced C-N to get strengthened as understood from incremental blue shifting of the band from 1250 to 1259 cm^{-1} . Similarly, the free C=O stretching at 1720 cm^{-1} is also not visible in PS bearing 100% ϕ_2 PDMS as macroglycol component in the elastomer (Fig. S7).

The absorption hovering near 1100 cm^{-1} indicates the presence of -O- group in all the elastomeric samples of PU (C-O-C), PUPS (C-O-C and Si-O-Si) and PS (Si-O-Si) (Figs. S2–S7)^{14,17}. With the incorporation of ϕ_2 PDMS components, it appears the shorter absorption at 997 cm^{-1} (Fig. S2) is blue shifted to 1013 cm^{-1} (Fig. S7). It may be noted that all these elastomers contain ether groups (-O-) but such ether

groups at the central part of the macroglycol components are exposed to symmetrical environment whereas those at the ends are unsymmetrical¹⁴ in nature because of their proximity to the amide groups in the elastomeric samples. Thus, for such unsymmetrical¹⁴ ether groups in the macroglycol segments, some C-O bonds couple to give symmetric stretching absorption¹⁴ at relatively lower wave number (997, 1005, 1014, 1014, 1015, 1013 cm^{-1}) corresponding to respective samples from PU through PS (Figs. S2–S7), compared to anti-symmetric C-O stretching (1103, 1102, 1102, 1102, 1100, 1060 cm^{-1}) corresponding to respective samples from PU through PS (Figs. S2–S7). It may be noted that in all these urethanes, the symmetric C-O shows, by and large, a gradual blue shift whereas the corresponding *anti*-symmetric exhibits gradual red shifting with the incorporation of ϕ_2 PDMS component in the elastomers.

The FTIR absorption of Si-O-Si appears to show different behaviour from that of C-O-C in the environment; illustratively the shorter absorption pattern at 1060 cm^{-1} for PS (Fig. S7) changed gradually to a more intense absorption (longer absorption pattern) until reached to PU at 1103 cm^{-1} (Fig. S2). On the other hand, the longer pattern of absorption at 1013 cm^{-1} for PS changed gradually to a shorter absorption pattern at 997 cm^{-1} until reached to PU (Fig. S2). Thus, the shorter pattern of absorption changed to longer absorption pattern with the change in environment due to decrease in the ratio of Si-O-Si/C-O-C segment and vice-versa.

Amides have a very strong tendency to self association by hydrogen bonding¹⁴, and the appearance of the spectrum is very much dependent on the physical state of the sample. Considerable shift in band positions has occurred on passing from one ambience to another, thus N-H and C=O stretching bands show a marked shift to lower frequency. Bands resulting from the secondary N-H bending vibrations appear near 1535–1564 cm^{-1} in solid phase (Figs. 3, S2–S7). Here the 1550 cm^{-1} band is not a simple N-H bending mode, but appears to result from coupling of this deformation with a C-N stretching vibrations¹⁴ as well.

Characteristic amide bands of such PU, PS and PUPS include the amide I, amide II and amide III^{14,18}. The absorption associated with the amide I band leads to stretching vibrations of the C=O bond of the amide, whereas the amide II, amide III bands lead primarily to different bending vibra-

tions of the N-H bond (Fig. 4). Because both the C=O and the N-H bonds are involved in the different types of hydrogen bonding (Fig. 5) that take place between the different elements, the locations of both the amide I and amide II bands are sensitive to the “backbone” of conformation^{14,17,18} of PU, PS and PUPS. The vibrational mode is directly related to the

Fig. 4. Different hydrogen bondings (HB1, HB2) through NH and oxygen atoms in which there are free CO and hydrogen bonded CO as well as free NH and hydrogen bonded NH of amide groups.

polymer “backbone” conformation¹⁹. The absorption of C-O and C=O derived from isocyanate group is visible near 1680 and 1720 cm^{-1} respectively (Figs. S2, S6). There is a peak at 1720 cm^{-1} corresponds to *free* C=O stretching in all PUPS elastomers irrespective of the ratio of macroglycols in urethane system; however it tends to show a red shift for elastomeric composition changing from PU to PS. 1687, 1680, 1680, 1680, 1625 cm^{-1} corresponds to C=O stretching (increasing C-O character than C=O) in urethane. But there is blue shift from 1535, 1539, 1539, 1542, 1545, 1564 cm^{-1} corresponds to N-H bending in urethane (Fig. S2) in which interestingly, such band of N-H bending is blue shifted slightly with the incorporation of ϕ_2 PDMS in the elastomer system (Figs. S2–S7). Clearly N-H bending is restricted but the C=O is changed remarkably to acquire some C-O character and influenced C-N to get strengthened as understood from incremental blue shifting of the band from 1250 to 1259 cm^{-1} ; and by and large such blue shifting taking place with the incorporation of ϕ_2 PDMS moiety in the elastomer (Figs. 3, S2–S7). Thus from the details of FTIR spectra, formation of products such as PU, PUPSs, PS is achieved.

Solvent absorption property of the elastomers:

Solvent absorption property as shown in Table 1 was de-

Fig. 5. Thermal degradation profile of different elastomers (PU, PS and PUPS) obtained by TGA at a heating rate of 10°C/min (1: PS-0 PTG/100 ϕ_2 PDMS; 2: PUPS-60 PTG/40 ϕ_2 PDMS; 3: PUPS-70 PTG/30 ϕ_2 PDMS; 4: PUPS-80 PTG/20 ϕ_2 PDMS; 5: PU-100 PTG/0 ϕ_2 PDMS).

Table 1. Absorption of solvents by PU and ϕ_2 PDMS modified elastomer (PUPS) immersed in solvents for 100 h time at 26°C temperature

Sample prepared from polyurethane containing different proportion of PTMO and $\alpha\omega$ OH ϕ PDMS in different elastomers	Wt.% of THF absorbed ($\delta_{\text{THF}} = 18.5$ MPa ^{1/2})	Wt.% of hexane absorbed ($\delta_{\text{hex}} = 14.9$ MPa ^{1/2})	Wt.% of water absorbed ($\delta_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = 48.0$ MPa ^{1/2})
PU-100 PTG/0 ϕ_2 PDMS	191	38.44	1.37
PUPS-90 PTG/10 ϕ_2 PDMS	180	25.09	0.82
PUPS-80 PTG/20 ϕ_2 PDMS	171	19.84	0.70
PUPS-70 PTG/30 ϕ_2 PDMS	100	17.37	0.68
PUPS-60 PTG/40 ϕ_2 PDMS	47	4.49	0.65
PS-0 PTG/100 ϕ_2 PDMS	10	4.41	0.61

terminated by measuring weight gain for a given time in accordance with the method²⁰ laid down in Ref. 20. From the Table 1, it indicates the absorption of solvents having different solubility parameters ($\delta_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} = 22.31 \text{ cal}^{1/2} \text{ cm}^{-3/2}$, $\delta_{\text{hex}} = 7.24 \text{ cal}^{1/2} \text{ cm}^{-3/2}$), $\delta_{\text{THF}} = 9.52 \text{ cal}^{1/2} \text{ cm}^{-3/2}$)^{21,22} for given period of time of 100 h decreases with the % increase in the ϕ_2 PDMS composition in the PUPS elastomer. It can be understood from the % water absorption data that the hydrophobic character of the PUPS samples increases with the incorporation of ϕ_2 PDMS macroglycol component in the PUPS elastomer network system. It may be noted that here the extent of absorption of organic solvent like n-hexane, THF is higher than

that of inorganic solvent like water, but such organic solvent followed the same trend as water did with such PUPS elastomer system. The increase in absorption with organic solvent in the matrix is mainly due to the increase in organic content of the PUPS elastomer system in commensurate with the statement "like favours like"¹⁴. The polarity is not the exclusive factor to influence the absorption of the solvent in such elastomers; n-hexane is less polar than water but has organic group similar to that of the aliphatic hexamethylene moiety of HDI. The increase in absorption is more in case of THF as it has polar ether group as well as its methylene moieties similar to that of PTG.

Thermal degradation property:

The TGA profile clearly indicates that in the given condition of heating rate all of these elastomers are thermally quite stable upto 200°C. Thermogravimetric analytical data as shown in Fig. 5 indicates that the Char yield at 500°C is maximum for PS (100% ϕ_2 PDMS as the macroglycol component) and decreases with decreasing content of ϕ_2 PDMS in the elastomer composition; and for system corresponding to PU (100% PTG as the macroglycol component) has minimum Char yield; interestingly, the results are in commensurate with the trend of decreasing Char yield with the decrease of inorganic moiety in the elastomer system²³. Thus the thermal stability is directly influenced by the composition of macroglycols in the elastomer sample.

Conclusion

This work demonstrates a methodology for modification of polyurethane resin through incorporation of telechelic dihydroxyl diphenyl dimethyl siloxane (PDMS) moiety into the matrix resin. This provides a scope to tailor the properties of polyurethane elastomer system as can be understood from the results of thermogravimetric analysis and solvent absorption studies. The hydrophobic character of such elastomers increases with the incorporation of PDMS moiety into the elastomer system. And in the given condition such elastomers tend to show better thermal stability with the enrichment of PDMS component in the elastomer matrix system.

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